

Table S.1: plastic composition and embodied exergy of critical car parts in SEAT Ibiza IV REF

Car part	Plastic		EE (g)	Othe (g)	E/P (g)	PP (g)	NR (g)	PA (g)	PU (g)	PE (g)	EPD M (g)	PET (g)	ABS (g)	PC (g)	PVC (g)	PO M (g)	PVBSBR (g)	PM MA (g)	VM Q (g)	FK M (g)	AC M (g)	EVO H (g)	ECO (g)	PS (g)	PPS (g)	PES (g)	
	mass(MJ)	rs (g)																									
Front cover	7,311.38	180.76	1,143.04	2,147.53	677.62	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3,238.67	87.30	0.00	17.23	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Fuel tank	7,485.75	166.92	243.31	0.00	3.01	0.00	76.20	1.00	0.00	6,669.08	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.90	453.78	0.00	0.00	1.36	2.92	0.00	9.02	0.00	0.00	26.16	0.00	
Rear cover	4,871.00	138.12	45.08	4,108.38	0.00	0.00	3.82	0.00	0.00	34.77	0.00	0.00	0.00	59.72	0.00	0.00	0.00	35.97	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Door trim panel front	4,278.56	137.53	13.00	2,126.28	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Front lighting	3,762.00	123.49	134.66	0.00	425.11	0.00	58.92	0.00	3.26	0.32	0.29	0.00	0.00	592.15	4.20	5.23	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	77.55	0.00	0.00	
Rear lighting	2,317.85	120.98	107.15	0.00	33.00	0.00	14.38	0.00	0.00	1.63	0.00	0.00	0.00	832.00	0.76	0.00	0.00	170.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Backrest pad	2,798.40	113.39	16.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1,364.00	0.00	0.00	14.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.20	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Plastic foam rear seat	2,834.00	110.33	145.68	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2,688.33	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Door trim panel rear	3,162.00	101.20	16.40	1,564.60	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Foam part seat	2,461.00	96.43	120.64	0.00	0.00	0.00	11.10	2,327.07	0.00	0.00	5.24	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Floor covering	3,400.00	88.86	551.56	157.60	674.49	0.00	7.47	0.00	2,152.90	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	63.57	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Seat padding	2,153.20	87.87	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1,070.60	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Wheel trim	1,396.00	78.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1,396.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Radiator Shroud	1,170.00	69.40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1,170.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Cover (engine)	1,648.26	66.07	387.80	0.00	0.00	0.00	785.00	475.00	0.46	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Cd-enhancing under	1,680.00	64.74	0.00	0.00	1,660.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	

Rear cover	4,883. 32	183 .53	36. 44	1,2 19. 00	3,5 03. 00	0.0	11. 88	0.0	7.2 0	1.3 2	41. 28	0.0	63. 20	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Fuel tank	7,803. 94	179 .89	66. 41	0.0	6.0 9	0.0	158 .05	0.0	6,9 70. 21	0.0	0.3 7	0.0	0.0	26. 44	553 .67	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.2 0	2.9 4	0.0	15. 58	0.0	0.9 7	0.0	0.0
Front lighting	4,537. 24	179 .58	131 .31	0.0	1,4 66. 28	0.0	170 .50	0.0	108 .85	11. 16	0.3 8	0.0	1,5 57. 00	0.0	31. 76	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,0 60. 00	0.0	0.0
Door trim panel front	5,328. 00	176 .47	0.0	2,5 02. 00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	72. 00	0.0	90. 00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Door trim panel rear	4,540. 00	153 .39	0.0	2,1 79. 00	4.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	87. 00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Floor covering	3,119. 30	150 .41	0.0	0.0	581 .30	0.0	19. 28	0.0	219 .05	0.0	2,1 37. 77	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	161 .90	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Wheel trim	2,020. 00	119 .83	0.0	0.0	0.0	2,0 20. 00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Plastic front	2,901. 00	113 .14	0.0	0.0	2,9 01. 00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Backrest pad	2,385. 70	97. 16	0.0	0.0	0.0	2,3 60. 00	0.0	0.8	0.0	5.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	19. 30	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Cd-enhancing underbody panel	2,468. 80	94. 70	0.0	0.0	1,2 14. 10	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	20. 30	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Floor sound insulation	3,900. 00	92. 20	780 .00	0.0	0.0	0.0	975 .00	2,1 45. 00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Glove compartment	2,508. 12	82. 54	6.1 9	2,4 38. 40	1.3	0.0	41. 70	0.0	0.0	6.4	0.0	0.1 1	11. 28	0.0	1.9 7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7 4	0.0	0.0
Seat padding	1,910. 29	77. 32	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,8 83. 60	0.7 2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	25. 97	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Cover	1,296. 86	71. 41	10. 00	0.0	0.0	996 .00	264 .00	0.4 6	26. 40	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Damping	2,958. 53	70. 72	1,2 23. 33	12. 20	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,7 00. 00	23. 00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Shield	1,677. 80	67. 52	0.0	0.0	1,5 06. 60	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	171 .20	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Trunk lid	1,752. 93	66. 96	0.0	0.0	1,6 68. 00	0.0	0.0	1.2 7	76. 10	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	7.5 6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Lining, trunk lid	1,977. 60	64. 18	0.0	1,9 68. 00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	9.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Plastic foam rear seat	1,482. 22	60. 18	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,4 66. 40	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	15. 82	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

